

THE EFFECT OF VALUES AND LIFESTYLES ON EATING OUT EXPECTATION

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to reveal the effect of values and lifestyles on the expectation of eating out. The quantitative research method was used in the study. In that respect, a survey technique was applied to 441 domestic tourists, which were involved in food and beverage activities at 6 touristic restaurant entrepreneurs. As a result of the survey research applied, it was concluded that the values and lifestyles of the participants affect the expectations of the atmosphere & aesthetics and locality from the restaurants. In addition, it has been determined that many personality traits have a positive correlation with eating out expectation. Therefore, it is thought that it will help food and beverage enterprises to analyze their target markets from this point of view and to maintain a more efficient business life by carrying out their activities such as establishment phases, service standards and marketing strategies.

Keywords: VALS. Restaurant. Eating Out. Psychographic Segmentation.

O EFEITO DOS VALORES E ESTILOS DE VIDA NAS EXPECTATIVAS EM COMER FORA

Resumo

O objetivo deste estudo é revelar o efeito de valores e estilos de vida na expectativa de comer fora. O método quantitativo de pesquisa foi utilizado no estudo. Nesse sentido, uma técnica de pesquisa *survey* foi aplicada a 441 turistas domésticos, envolvidos em atividades de alimentos e bebidas em 6 empresários de restaurantes turísticos. Como resultado da pesquisa aplicada, concluiu-se que os valores e estilos de vida dos participantes afetam as expectativas da atmosfera, estética e localidade dos restaurantes. Além disso, foi determinado que muitos traços de personalidade têm uma correlação positiva com a expectativa de comer fora. Portanto, acredita-se que ajudará as empresas de alimentos e bebidas a analisar seus mercados-alvo desse ponto de vista e a manter uma vida comercial mais eficiente, realizando suas atividades como fases de estabelecimento, padrões de serviço e estratégias de marketing.

Palavras chave: VALS. Restaurante. Comer Fora. Segmentação Psicográfica.

EL EFECTO DE LOS VALORES Y ESTILOS DE VIDA EN LAS EXPECTATIVAS DE COMER FUERA

Resumen

El propósito de este estudio es revelar el efecto de los valores y estilos de vida en la expectativa de comer fuera. El método de investigación cuantitativa se utilizó en el estudio. A ese respecto, se aplicó una técnica de encuesta a 441 turistas nacionales, que participaron en actividades de alimentos y bebidas en 6 empresarios de restaurantes turísticos. Como resultado de la investigación de la encuesta aplicada, se concluyó que los valores y estilos de vida de los participantes afectan las expectativas del ambiente y la estética y la localidad de los restaurantes. Además, se ha determinado que muchos rasgos de personalidad tienen una correlación positiva con la expectativa de comer fuera. Por lo tanto, se cree que ayudará a las empresas de alimentos y bebidas a analizar sus mercados objetivo desde este punto de vista y a mantener una vida comercial más eficiente mediante la realización de sus actividades, como las fases de establecimiento, los estándares de servicio y las estrategias de marketing.

Palabras clave: VALS. Restaurante. Comer Fuera. Segmentación Psicográfica.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Within the retrospective process, humanity has been migrated and travelled for various reasons. From creativity until today, human has continuously moved (dislocated) in order to discover new settlements, to be away from disasters and for some reasons such as commercial and religious bases. Among all, the major expedition reason is to meet the nutrition requirement. Food requirement has usually met with external production and presentation (Karamustafa and Ülker, 2018, p. 22).

Restaurant entrepreneurs are the leading examples of this. Today, the food and beverage sector is under fierce competition. A wide range of products and continuously changing habits of people make restaurants difficult to be achieved and sustainable; and this issue leads to a base to make competition become harder (Yıldız, 2010, p. 23). In that respect, continuous customer increase leads to the forming of loyal customers and makes restaurants survive under the competitive market conditions.

The broadest way to evaluate loyalty as a significant consumer reaction is to focus on the implications to be implemented by determining the factors that would affect consumer preferences at restaurant industry (Clark & Wood, 1998). When we look at consumer preferences, lifestyles are important. Just because individuals have the same age or income does not mean that they will make the same choice. Consumer groups, consisting of different personal factors and the whole of social factors, constitute the need for people to be categorized according to their lifestyle rather than individual variables (Kotler & Armstrong, 2013).

In today's competitive environment, a deeper consumer understanding is needed in order for businesses to effectively set targets and choose their goods/services (Boedeker, 1995). The behaviour process, which is finalised with having fun, preferring, selecting and purchasing, comprises food and beverage consumption. This process is affected by the components related to food, environment, and individuals. Psychological, physiological and cultural factors are indicated as individual related components (Yıldırım Saçılık, 2017).

According to Abbey (1979), Tourism Research is divided into two on the basis of demographics (Silva, Kushano & Avila, 2008; Muñoz-Fernández et al., 2017) and behaviour. Behavior analysis attempts to explain the reasons behind expectations, and to study tourists, the most popular research approach is lifestyle analysis. Woodside and Pitts (1976) mentioned that individuals' values and lifestyles may

be more important than demographic variables in predicting touristic behavior.

Within the recent marketing concept, providing customer satisfaction has become the major argument to sustain under fierce market competition (Kamat et al., 2017) from the perspective of restaurant entrepreneurs. To provide satisfaction, the ideal way is to meet the expectations of the customers. People with differentiated expectations and distinction of the characteristics are the factors, which make expectations difficult to find common ground. This also reveals the purpose of the study.

There are a limited number of studies that empirically and conceptually measure lifestyle and motivations for eating out among tourists living in Turkey. Therefore, the research is a topic that could give the sector an important clue as to how to carry out domestic tourist expectation.

2 THEORETICAL REVIEW

2.1 Eating Out (Food & Beverage) Expectation

The concept of "expectation", which is defined as "thing expected to be realized" or considerations of individuals under certain conditions and situations or for the expected things" by the Turkish Language Institution (TLI), is ascribed a meaning to some issues i.e satisfaction, quality, loyalty from the point of recent restaurant entrepreneurs (Turkish Language Institution, 2019). In fact, "customer satisfaction" is defined as the implication of differentiated points between the perceived customers' expectation towards products and services and their experience following the use of this product (Burucuoğlu, 2011).

In another meaning, customer satisfaction or dissatisfaction explains the distinction between the customer expectancy and the reality led by consuming or using (Güven, 2010, p. 291). Customer satisfaction is a concept, which has directly proportional progress with the customer expectancy; it is related to the preferential expectations of individuals (Bulgan & Soybalı, 2011). Meeting with customer expectations leads to the formation of customer satisfaction.

Should a restaurant follow up-to-date progress and innovations, then it is possible to say that these restaurants are able to have implications on customers' preferential behaviours more accurately and effectively develop managing strategies accordingly. At that point, the most crucial element is to forecast what customer expectations are and to meet them. Hence, the customers carrying the belief that their expectation was not met and could not get the expected value following their consumption would be unhappy (Dalgiç et al., 2016).

A service, which is approved by customers may both increase customer satisfaction and have an effect on the re-visiting of these customers to the restaurant at a substantial level (Namkung & Jang, 2007).

Because expectations significantly affect consumers' food decisions, it is obvious that consumer expectations also affect food quality. In this sense, it is possible to define the best quality as consistency in consumer expectations (Cardello, 1995, p. 166). Any failure to meet with customer expectations will lead to customer dissatisfaction as well as the information share of those peoples' negative experiences with other people (Berry & Parasuraman, 1997).

Components of a good servicing that may be presented to the tourists in food and beverage entrepreneurs are stated as follows: meeting or over-meeting with customer expectations; awareness in food's benefits and specifications; paying close attention to visitors; behaving in a polite and kind way; having communicative skills; avoiding from using slang language and ability to have professional official relations with customers (Yalı, 2016). Expectation related to food and beverage experiences of a customer are evaluated respectively as below (Cousins et al., reviewed in 2014 by Ayaz & Yalı, 2017):

- Presented food and beverages
- Services (Silva, 2016)
- Hygiene and clean environment
- Paid price and commercial value
- Restaurant Atmosphere

Components directly affecting the selection criteria of people are determined as (Özdemir, 2010):

- Food quality
- Food variety (product range)
- Price
- Atmosphere
- Restaurant location

As indicated above, meal/food quality, price and value coherence and restaurant specifications carry prominence for their restaurant preferences as well as eating out expectations.

A food and beverage entrepreneur is a social structure as well as the main activities. Since people having differentiated expectancies and various requirements visit these places. (Rizaoğlu and Hançer, 2013, p. 46). Perceptions of customers related to service quality consist of customers' expectancies and these expectancies may vary in accordance with the personality characteristics of each of them (Shengelbayeva, 2009).

As various types of customers (with varied characteristics) may have differentiated requirements, restaurant personnel should consider what each of these customers might need and they should behave accordingly. (Kızılırmak, 1995). As well as customers may have differentiated expectations, common requirements and desires are at most level. These are listed as: meeting with their expectations in goods and services, care, reliability, product range (food & beverage variety), high technology, innovative methods, easy-use methods, ability to purchase the value of the price against purchased goods and services, comfort and convenience.

Customer expectations may differ from one to another. The components, which lead to these differences, are i.e having different income levels, having differentiated expenditure habits, being under different cultural atmosphere, belonging to differentiated social stratum, having location in differentiated geographical regions and the individual determinants (Aktepe, et al., 2009, p. 65).

2.2 Values and Lifestyle (VALS2)

The word "values" has commonly used by the social scientists originally with its Latin etymologic meaning (*valere: being valuable, being strong*). "Values", which sometimes ties with the materiality, have also been defined within the framework of "motives" and "objectives" at some points. For the term "values", which consists of many factors and have complicated meaning, it has not been possible to reveal an unambiguous definition until today. (Korkmaz, 2013: 53).

Should we make a few explanations in accordance with the objective of the related survey study; values as a conception may be expressed with differentiated meanings for instance objectives of any type of needs, attitude or will; to some extent it may be deemed as lifestyle, survival aim and to some extent social and cultural values (Özgüven, 2014).

Values are commonly known as objectives serving as pathways (guiding principles) in human life, carrying prominence and possible to change according to the situations. Value preferences of individuals are a part of their main worldviews. (Struch et al., 2002). "Values", from the view of individuals, may be asserted also with sociological terms determining what people pay attention to and what people consider as important (Avçıkurt, 2009: 110).

Thus, value perceptions of individuals may be considered as factors that take a decisive part in their social behaviours as well as being significant factors that directly or indirectly affect their attribute and decision-making mechanisms.

It is possible to state that; it serves as a guide to determine what type of individuals are included in the target market, what their interests are, what the possible ideal communication way is and what marketing strategies are (Lopes, Maia and Boubeta, 2010). In addition to this, it is possible to assert that; it gains us the favour of ability to evaluate it as a whole with the reasons led by the values, which affects the target market (Dülgeroğlu, 2008: 75).

Another component, which is commonly used to determine the behaviour and attitudes of the consumer individuals, is the lifestyle. It is possible to define a community-oriented map in order to separate communities, which have lifestyle stratum. Lifestyle, which also underlies cultural structures in itself, is an important factor to determine how to use product, service and time in the scope of consumption (Chaney, 1999: 15; Kahraman, 2011: 2).

In 1983, a lifestyle scale was produced by Mitchell. This scale, which was in a more sociological framework, revealed nine types of lifestyles approved rationally in order to focus on characteristic lifestyle in the United States of America. Following the re-consideration of various sets such as specific values and needs, he produced nine types of lifestyles (Kahle et al., 1986: 405; Horley et al., 1988: 384; Novak & MacEvoy, 1990: 105).

The development of VALS is based on Maslow's (1954) need hierarchy and social character concepts. While classifying people into one of the nine of lifestyle stratum through statistical and theoretical tools, he determined expressions that he had considered as useful and demographic questionnaire.

With a wide scope of research having been conducted in the United States of America, revealed primary life styles are classified as: survivors (4%), sustainers (7%), belongers (35%), emulators (9%), achievers (22%), "I-am-me" (5%), experiential (7%), societally conscious (9%) and integrated (2%) (Sharon et al., 1988). It is figured as a primary main theoretical psychographic system, which integrates the social values of people to the key motives of their lives.

For the reasons of developed and changes sociological structure as well as the high number of questionnaire statements included into the survey, some psychometric experts conducted a serial of researches in order to improve the scale and to decrease the number of these statements. Furthermore, the VALS scale used for market division has yet become unable to meet the requirements and launched to be exposed to many criticisms (Winters, 1989: 67). VALS Scale was developed then by Stanford Research Institute (SRI) and took part in the literature with its revised title as VALS2 (Schwardz, 1992; Thorgersen & Ölander, 2002).

As laid down by Figure.1, Values and Lifestyle (VALS2) Model has many sub-dimensions. These obtained sub-dimensions basically illustrate the consumer groups located in America. This psychographic scale, which has been applied to different country people, outputs differentiated results. As Turkey has not any values and lifestyle model, which has been commonly agreed on and applicable by the researches, studies, in general, are based on American viewed values and lifestyle model.

Sub-dimensions of the VALS 2 Model and the attribution of participants to be involved in any of these dimensions were clarified by the SRI (Stanford Research Institute) (SRI, 2019) as follows:

Innovators: Consumer groups classified under innovators dimension are comprised of the individuals who are always in favour of taking in information and have high perception levels (antennas up). Furthermore, they make high number of financial transactions and act in a sceptical way regarding advertising. This future-oriented consumer group depends on Research & Development as well as science. The groups are comprised of individuals who are receptive to new ideas and technologies, willing to solve problems and have a wide variety of interests and activities (SRI, 2019).

Figure 1: The VALS Framework.

Source: Stanford Research Institute (2019); Kurtz et al., (2009. p. 276).

Thinkers: The individuals involved into this group are comprised of the individuals who compare ideas i.e what should social behaviour be and what social behaviour ought to be. They make plans, researches before taking action and try to make

decisions through analysing. This group, which is financially constant, functionally use technology, prefer traditional intellectual pursuits and purchase proven products (SRI, 2019).

Believers: This group is comprised of the individuals, who think that they would lead a good life through believing in basic rights and wrongs. They want friendly communities and watch TV or read romantic books in order to relaxation or calming down. They do not have any tolerance to ambiguity; they do not have tendency to change society. They view advertising as a rational source of information. Furthermore, they are deemed as loyal and consistent/stable customer types (SRI, 2019).

Achievers: This group is comprised of the individuals who have an attitude of “me first, my family first” and believe that the money is the source of authority and committed to family and job. They are fully scheduled, goal-oriented, hardworking, moderate and peer conscious. Furthermore, it is possible to say that this group is comprised of private and professional individuals. They tend to prefer prestigious products and services (SRI, 2019).

Strivers: As a consumption group, resources and achievement motives of the Strivers are low. It is comprised of individuals, who have a high tendency to change the job and high temporary unemployment. They use video and video games as a form of fantasy. Furthermore, this is a consumption group, who are entertaining, fun-loving, imitative and intensively use public transportation, interact with street culture, have a continuous desire to better their lives but have difficulty in realizing their desire (SRI, 2019).

Experiencers: As a consumption group, experiencers have high resources and self-expression motivation. They have an attitude that they want everything. They are individuals who are up on the latest fashions, seek variety and sensation, love physical activities, view themselves as social people, believe that friends are extremely important and they are classified in a consumption group, which make expenditures in this regard (SRI, 2019).

Makers: As a consumption group, Makers have low resources and a self-expression motivation. They are distrustful of government; have a strong interest in everything related to automotive, have strong outdoor interests (i.e hunting, fishing, etc.), view trials and repairing as a mission. They may be characterized as practical people who have hand skills. They act based on values quite more than luxury products and they have tendency to expend for highly basic needs (SRI, 2019).

Survivors: As a consumption group, survivors have the lowest resources and do not exhibit primary motivation. Survivors, who live in a confined space,

believe that the world is changing caused by lack of resources. They stand by familiar ones and trust has the top priority. The obligation to satisfy the basic needs leads them to unable to exhibit any primary motivation in a strong manner. They represent a moderate market; they are dependent on their favorite brand, pay attention to discounts (SRI, 2019).

As can be seen by the Stanford Research Institute by dividing consumer groups into psychographic segmentation, the common characteristics of each consumer group are also stated. VALS, which can be applied to all good/service consumer groups, is planned to be applied to domestic tourists who are a service consumer in this study.

The values and lifestyle model help increase the ability to predict tourist behavior. The VALS study helps us understand how tourists spend their money and time, how they make their choices. It is also useful in understanding the tourist's motivation and expectation. Based on the philosophy that psychological traits and demographics are stronger than just demographics, the VALS now uses psychology to describe the dynamics underlying tourist preferences, expectations and choices.

Accordingly, the research model and hypotheses of the study was proposed as stated below:

H₁: There is a significant effect of values and lifestyles on hygiene & service expectation.

H₂: There is a significant effect of values and lifestyles on locality expectation.

H₃: There is a significant effect of values and lifestyles on atmosphere & aesthetics expectation.

Figure 2: Research Model.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

3 METHODOLOGY

Objective and prominence, the methodology of the research, population, sample and constraints related to the research and data analysis will be given.

3.1 Objective and Prominence of the Research

As the subject here is human, the restaurant sector serves a social environment for guests as well

as dealing with commercial activity. Under fierce competitive conditions and considering the unstable structure; recognizing customers and providing customer loyalty have crucial significance for restaurants to survive.

The objective of this research is to reveal the correlation between eating out expectations through psychographic classification (values and lifestyles) of domestic tourist who have been involved in food and beverage activities in the restaurants, which have been activated in a touristic destination such as Sapanca.

3.2 Research Methodology

In order to analyse the correlation between the lifestyles and eating out expectation of the domestic tourists who have purchased food and beverage services from the restaurants operating in Sapanca, data is collected through survey study as one of the quantitative research methods. To produce the survey, appropriate scale is selected through secondary data research.

The survey is consisted of 3 units: In the first two parts of the survey, 5 point likert-type (I fully disagree - I fully agree) scales are used. Values and life style scale (VALS2), which is consisted of 35 questions and included into the first unit, has been developed by the Stanford Research Institute (SRI); became a basis for many researches at national and international level.

The eating out expectation scale, which is comprised of 20 questions, used by Yalı (2016) in his research comprises the second unit. The scale of eating out expectations was revised to 16 questions with expert opinions and pilot survey. As a result of the pilot survey analyse, 2 questions were removed from the questionnaire and data collection was continued. As for the final unit, demographic questions comprised of 6 sentences were included.

As a sampling technique, purposive sampling which is a kind of sampling that does not based on possibility is chosen in the research. In the purposive sampling, test subjects do not taken randomly; hence, there the researches need to select the people who will reply to the questions to the research problems (Coşkun et al., 2015, p. 142). Participants were selected with the help of two criteria that we determined with the non-probability sampling method. The first of these criteria is to be 18 years of age and over, the second is to be a person who has come to the destination for touristic purposes.

3.3 Population and Sampling Method

Universe-population of the research is comprised of the domestic tourist, who have been involved in

food and beverages activities in the restaurant entrepreneurs, which are activating in Sapanca. At first, restaurant owners/managers of the restaurants activating in Sapanca, were interviewed with, they were shared with information, and necessary approvals were taken. Between the dates 2018 December and 2019 March 441 customers were included into the sampling during their eating out activity in the restaurant.

Data is collected through face-to-face survey at weekends (Saturday-Sunday) by the researchers. The reason why weekends were selected is; high number of occupancy rate in the related entrepreneurs and to reach to the wider social stratum. In addition, daily touristic tours to the Sapanca destination are usually held on weekends. For this reason, the data collection phase was more efficient at the weekend.

3.4 Data Analysis

Data obtained in this research is conducted through SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) program. In order to determine how data indicated a distribution, Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is used during the analysis process of the study. In addition to this, skewness and kurtosis values of the data are considered. At the end of conducted research, it is analysed that the data is normally distributed and parametric tests are selected in data analysis.

As consequence of the implemented normality test, demographic specifications of the participants and related frequency rate are obtained through frequency analysis and it is reported. Scales of life style and eating out expectation are analysed with factor analysis and afterwards, in order to determine the correlation between the life style and the eating out expectation, correlation and regression tests are conducted. Implemented tests are detailed by the following tables and they are tried to be explained through those tables.

4 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Data obtained from the studying environment is tabulated through analysing by SPSS program. In this scope, frequency, factor, regression and correlation analysis are done.

For each scale used in the study, reliability analyses are applied. When Table 1 is examined, at first, reliability test analysis are applied to 35 statements, which are included into the "Life style (VALS)" scale and Cronbach Alpha co-efficiency is determined as 0,776. After that, as consequence of reliability analysis of 14 statements included into the

“Eating Out Expectations”, Cronbach Alpha coefficient is determined as 0,933 and it is possible to say that applied scales are at high reliability level. It is stated that; while Alpha coefficient is expected as at least 0,5 in social sciences, scales which reveals 0,7 and higher results have high reliability (Coşkun et al., 2015, p. 126).

Following the application of reliability analysis onto the survey scales, whole of both scales are again subjected to a reliability analysis under the title general scale. The relevant scales will be subjected to exploratory factor analysis as they contain many expressions. For this reason, the overall reliability coefficient of the scales is quoted in the related table.

Table 1: Reliability Analysis Results of The Research Scales

Scale	Number of Statements	Cronbach Alpha
VALS Scale	35	0,763
Eating Out Expectation Scale	14	0,943
Overall	49	0,894

Source: prepared by the authors

Hence Cronbach Alpha coefficient of the overall scale is determined as 0,892, it is possible to state that all of the scales as a whole provide reliability requirement and therefore they are applicable for statistical analysis. Furthermore, it is possible to express that the scales, which have been used for this research, carry the reliability criteria considering

that these scales had been used in order to find answers to the same survey questions before.

As consequence of the applied reliability analysis, frequency values related to the demographic correlation of the participants who have purchased food and beverage services in the restaurants are listed by the Table 2 below.

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics of Participants.

Variables	n	%
Gender		
Female	270	61,2
Male	171	38,8
Marital Status		
Married	189	44,4
Single	252	55,6
Age		
Between 18- 25 ages	106	24
Between 26- 35 ages	186	42,2
Between 36- 45 ages	100	22,7
56 and older	49	11,1
Graduation Status		
Primary school	22	5
High school and equivalent	64	14,5
Pre-graduate school	62	14,1
Graduate School	201	45,6
Post-graduate (Master/PhD)	92	20,9
Vocation		
Retired	8	1,8
Public (Officer/Official)	109	24,7
Private Sector	209	47,4
Student	53	12
Housewife	22	5
Other	40	9,1
Income Level		
Minimum Wage	50	11,3
360 - 464 USD	93	21,1
465 - 700 USD	104	23,6
701 - 930 USD	96	21,8
931 USD and higher amount	98	22,2

Source: Prepared by the authors (USD: United States Dollar).

When above table 2 is examined, it is seen that the participants are intensively at 26-35 ages. When the educational situation of new participants is considered, it will be true to say that, 43% of these people are graduate students. When vocational status of the participants is considered, it is clear that nearly half of the participants (46,6%) are private sector personnel and also private sector personnel is followed by public personnel (25,6%). As consequence of this situation, it is possible to mention that individuals who have income at certain level tend to purchase food and beverages services.

When looking at the frequency values of the participants, it is seen that there is nearly an equal

distribution. Factor analysis results providing the classification of value and lifestyle scale related to the statements that are classified into sub-dimensions are laid down by the Table-3 below.

According to factor analysis given by the Table 3, "values and lifestyle" of the participants are classified under eight different dimensions as follows: self-expressioners, experiencers, makers, innovators, leaders, believers, thinkers and survivors. For each dimensions in the framework of statistical analysis Cronbach Alpha, Arithmetical Average and expressed variance values are mentioned in the related table.

Table 3: Factor Analysis of Expressions Regarding Values & Lifestyles of Participants.

Achievement	Exp.Variance 14,111	Arith. Average	Std. Deviation	Factor Load
I follow the latest fashion and trends		2,98	1,277	0,889
I wear more appropriate to fashion comparing to that of other people		3,04	1,213	0,863
I like wearing appropriate to the latest fashion		2,78	1,226	0,860
I like to be known as fashion follower		2,46	1,289	0,814
I must admit that I love showing off		2,44	1,240	0,568
Experiencers	Exp. Variance 13,863	Arith. Average	Std. Deviation	Factor Load
Excitement is a passion for me		3,72	0,975	0,803
I generally look for excitement		3,49	1,010	0,800
I love excessive excitement		3,33	1,021	0,761
I like changes very much related to my life		3,13	1,227	0,579
I like trying new things		4,17	0,856	0,465
Makers	Exp. Variance 7,896	Arith. Average	Std. Deviation	Factor Load
I like dealing with handcrafts		3,24	1,375	0,848
I like producing something such as wooden, metallic materials		3,31	1,399	0,817
I prefer producing on my own instead of purchasing		3,35	1,268	0,757
I love producing something to use in daily life		3,92	1,020	0,545
Innovators	Exp. Variance 6,671	Arith. Average	Std. Deviation	Factor Load
I like new and different things		4,14	0,999	0,752
I like trying something which has not been tried before		3,86	0,973	0,701
I like learning even it may never work		3,83	1,135	0,613
I like extraordinary people and objects		3,79	1,070	0,611
I like learning something related to art, cultural and historical fields.		4,15	1,021	0,522
Leaders	Exp. Variance 5,433	Arith. Average	Std. Deviation	Factor Load
I like leading to other people		3,76	1,047	0,828
I like taking responsibility of a group		3,78	1,009	0,778
I can define myself as an intelligent individual		3,37	0,979	0,548
I am more talented than many people		3,46	0,964	0,462
Believers	Exp. Variance 4,924	Arith. Average	Std. Deviation	Factor Load
Religious education shall be increased in public schools		2,38	1,271	0,798
To me, the world has been created in 6 days as it is written in holly books		2,74	1,325	0,737
Recently sexuality has been come onto the forefront on TVs.		3,43	1,339	0,573
If a woman provides a happy family atmosphere her life becomes meaningful.		2,83	1,527	0,565
Thinkers	Exp. Variance 4,223	Arith. Average	Std. Deviation	Factor Load

I like learning further information related to the function of the universe	4,28	0,910	0,725
I am often interested in theories	3,35	1,033	0,716
Survivors	Exp. Variance 3,892	Arith. Average	Std. Deviation
I simply deal with a few things in my life.	2,59	1,237	0,719
I should accept that my interest area is limited.	2,67	1,347	0,656
I want my life more regular from week to week.	3,72	1,032	0,595

Direct Oblimin Rotated Major Component Analysis: Explained Total Variance: 61,014%; Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Sampling Size: 67,1%; Barlett Globality Test (0,00): $p < 0,05$; df. 59, Evaluation interval (For all dimensions [1] I fully disagree – [5] I fully agree)

Source: prepared by the authors.

KMO (*Kaiser Mayer Olkin*) value, which measure the applicability of factor analysis is determined as 67,1% for Values and Life Style scale. It is seen that expressed total variance value is 61%. With this obtained data, it is clear that the factor analysis that has been conducted is significant and valid. Factor analysis results for food and beverages expectation scale are laid by the Table 4. As consequence of factor analysis, KMO value is determined as 87,4%.

As a result of this value, it is possible to say data set is applicable for the factor analysis. According to applied factor analysis, “eating out expectation” is classified under 3 dimensions with the following titles: 1) Hygiene and Service 2) Locality 3) Atmosphere and Aesthetics. In the framework of statistical coherency, for each of the dimensions arithmetic average, standard deviation and variance value are clearly defined.

Table 4: Factor Analysis Based on Eating Out Expectation Scale

Hygiene and Service Quality	Exp. Variance 52,424	Arith. Average	Std. Deviation	Factor Load
I care restaurant personnel be in comply with the hygiene rules		4,64	0,834	,903
I care tastes of meals		4,72	0,764	,896
I care cleaning of the meal hall		4,65	0,877	,863
I care cleaning of service equipments (table, plate, fork, napkin, tablecloth etc.) used in presentation of food and beverages		4,71	0,773	,860
I recommend that meals should be served hot.		4,64	0,812	,854
I pay attention to the cleaning of the hall at which food and beverages are served		4,65	0,854	,836
I pay attention that wc and washbasins at food and beverage serving restaurants are clean.		4,70	0,782	,763
I care the interest of restaurant personnel		4,52	0,888	,607
Locality	Exp. Variance 9,973	Arith. Average	Std. Deviation	Factor Load
I care that local meals are included into menus		4,03	1,197	,932
I care testing local meals		4,24	1,060	,849
I care that the meals are organic		4,03	1,078	,651
Atmosphere and Aesthetics	Exp. Variance 8,099	Arith. Average	Std. Deviation	Factor Load
I care the modernity of meal halls.		3,56	1,192	,915
I care the appearance of meals		4,25	0,992	,603
I care quietness of the meal hall.		4,14	1,088	,505

Direct Oblimin Rotated Major Component Analysis: Explained Total Variance: %70,496; Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Sampling Size: % 87,4; Barlett Globality Test (0,00): $p < 0,05$; df. 91, Evaluation Interval (For all dimensions [1] fully disagree– [5] fully agree).

Source: prepared by the authors.

The statement, which has the highest factor load at hygiene and service quality level is “I care restaurant personnel be in comply with the hygiene rules”. (0,903) At locality level, the statement of “I care that local meals are included into menus (0,932)” is believed to be the statement which has the highest factor load. As another dimension under “Atmosphere and Aesthetics” level in the scale of eating out

expectation, the statement, which has the highest factor load, is “I care the modernity of meal halls (0,915)”. When overall load distribution of the dimensions is examined, it is true to say that factor loads are at satisfactory level. In order to determine the correlation between the obtained dimensions as a result of analysis, correlation analysis has been implemented as laid down by Table-5.

Table 5: Correlation Analysis for Determining Relationship Between Factors.

Variables	\bar{X}	S.S	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1-Achievement	2,77	1,113	1									
2-Experiencers	3,53	0,836	,126	1								
3-Makers	3,52	1,017	-,248**	,191*	1							
4-Innovators	4,05	0,866	-,012	,379**	,343**	1						
5-Leaders	3,73	0,752	,245**	,214*	,100	,311**	1					
6-Survivors	2,96	0,987	,214*	,150	-,142	-,028	-,043	1				
7-Hygiene/Serv.	4,71	0,727	,008	,033	,109	,275**	,182*	,033	1			
8-Locality	3,65	0,850	,224**	,478**	,180*	,337**	,741**	,008	,063	1		
9-Atmosphere	4,10	0,831	-,121	,141	,162	,500**	,134	-,050	,302**	,111	1	
10-Believers	3,03	1,047	,130	,114	,019	-,038	,169	,308**	,039	,102	,020	1
11-Thinkers	3,95	0,846	-,133	,097	,196*	,298**	,166	-,157	,258**	,115	,754**	-,094

Source: prepared by the authors. (*: 0,5 at level of significance, **:0,1 at level of significance).

Due the conducted correlation analysis, it is clear that there is a correlation at medium and high levels with positive and negative directions between the dimensions. When correlation co-efficiency is examined, there is a correlation with positive direction between the Hygiene & Service Quality and the Leaders at medium level (0,275**) and at low level (0,182*) respectively.

Regarding the Locality dimension, it is possible to express that there is a level of significance between the dimensions of Achievements (0,224**), Experiencers (0,478**), and Innovators (0,337). It is also determined that while there is a correlation at low level with positive direction between the Locality dimension and the Makers, there is a strong correlation with positive direction with the Leaders (0,741**).

When looking at the "Atmosphere" dimension, it is determined that there is a linear correlation at medium level with the Innovators (0,50**) dimension. It is analysed that there are many correlations including the positive and negative directions at low and high level, between each of many other dimensions. However, in accordance with the objective of this research, correlations between the related dimensions are tried to be interpreted.

In Table 6, regression analysis was performed in order to determine the effect between the dimensions of the scales analysed. In this section, dependent variables are hygiene & service quality, locality, atmosphere and aesthetic dimensions. The independent variables are achievement, experiencers, makers, innovators, leaders, survivors, believers, thinkers dimensions.

When the first part of the regression analysis is examined, it is seen that the whole model is not significant at the level of $p = 0.05$ (0,102). In other words, the whole model has no effect on the dimension of hygiene and service quality.

When the second part of the regression analysis is examined, it can be said that the whole model is significant at the level of $p=0.05$ (0,000) and independent variables according to the regression model in the second part can explain 64.3% of the change in dependent variables (Adjusted R Square: 0,643). When the third part is examined, it is seen that the model is still meaningful ($p=0.000$) and the independent variables in the model explain 24.4% of the change in dependent variables (Adjusted R Square: 0.244).

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics and Regression Analysis.

Independent Variables	Beta	Standard Error	t	P	R ²	Adj. R ²	Sig.
Achievement	,014	,032	,283	,777	,099	,041	0,102
Experiencers	-,132	,042	-2,721	,007			
Makers	-,020	,036	-,399	,690			
Innovators	,300	,047	5,421	,000			
Leaders	,082	,048	1,632	,103			
Believers	,195	,041	4,053	,000			
Survivors	,105	,036	2,170	,031			
Thinkers	-,002	,071	-,024	,981			
* Significance level of $p<0,05- 1$. Part. Dependent Variable: hygiene & service quality							
Independent Variables	Beta	Standard Error	t	P	R ²	Adj. R ²	Sig.
Achievement	,076	,025	2,322	,021	,664	,643	0,000
Experiencers	,286	,034	8,679	,000			
Makers	,139	,029	4,033	,000			
Innovators	-,024	,037	-,629	,529			

Leaders	,660	,038	19,388	,000			
Believers	-,023	,033	-,705	,481			
Survivors	,006	,028	,184	,854			
Thinkers	-,032	,056	-,562	,575			
<i>* Significance level of $p < 0,05$ – 2. Part. Dependent Variable: Locality</i>							
Independent Variables	Beta	Standard Error	t	P	R²	Adj. R²	Sig.
Achievement	-,036	,022	-1,212	,226	,290	,244	0,000
Experiencers	-,032	,030	-1,063	,288			
Makers	-,077	,026	-2,447	,015			
Innovators	,357	,033	10,350	,000			
Leaders	-,076	,034	-2,423	,016			
Believers	,682	,029	22,773	,000			
Survivors	,090	,025	2,972	,003			
Thinkers	-,148	,076	-1,816	,072			
<i>* Significance level of $p < 0,05$ – 3. Part. Dependent Variable: Atmosphere & Aesthetic</i>							

Source: Prepared by the authors.

The hypothesis test results of the study are given and interpreted in table 7 below:

Table 7: Hypotheses Results.

Hypotheses		Results
H ₁	There is a significant effect of values and lifestyles on hygiene & Service expectation	Not Supported
H ₂	There is a significant effect of values and lifestyles on locality expectation	Supported
H ₃	There is a significant effect of values and lifestyles on atmosphere & aesthetics expec.	Supported

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Looking at the general framework, it is seen that two of the hypotheses tested are supported. H₁ hypothesis did not produce meaningful results. However, it has been proved that the effect of the tourists on the locality dimension in their lifestyle and expectations of eating out. It is also determined that there is a significant relationship between the tourists who experiencers & innovators lifestyle groups and the locality dimension.

On the other hand, the effects of tourist values and lifestyles on some dimensions of expectation of eating out were determined. This occurred in the atmosphere and aesthetic dimension. It is seen that the food and beverage consumer cares about the atmosphere and aesthetics of the place they will go when they are eating out. It has been determined that there is a linear relationship between the tourist included in the innovator tourist group and the atmosphere & aesthetic dimension.

5 CONCLUSION

Food and beverage companies have to carry out effective marketing strategies in order to get their

share in the competitive environment of the tourism sector. Therefore, it is critical to have knowledge about the behavioral and psychological characteristics of tourists. It is known that values and lifestyles are used in related studies in order to explain the attitudes and behaviors of consumers. In today's competitive conditions, tourist profiles, values and lifestyles are becoming the determining factors at the point where goods and products are similar. In the light of these data, businesses use their goods or services to purchase or to be preferred.

It is aimed to determine the values and lifestyles of the tourists in food and beverage establishments and to determine how effective they are in the context of food and beverage expectations. In this respect, it is seen that the results and the descriptive factor analysis applied to the lifestyle scale are grouped under eight dimensions. These are achievement, experiencers, makers, innovators, leaders, survivors, believers, thinkers dimensions. Within the framework of these dimensions, it is tried to determine the relationships and effects in the expectations of the tourists about the food and beverage.

Considering the arithmetic averages of the responses of the participants to the expressions of food and beverage expectations, it is seen that the cleanliness of the service equipment used for the presentation is very important. It can be said that the participants give importance to the physical hygiene of the equipment in food and beverage enterprises. It is also an impressive factor in eating out expectation.

Based on the findings, it can be said that the participants included in the research sample gave importance to experimenting with local foods and food presentation. Today, it is known that locality has an important place for tourist in gastronomic expectations (Pimentel & Machado, 2014, p.27; Fusté-Forné, 2017; Çalışkan et al., 2019). As a result of the correlation analysis related to the purpose of the study, it was found that there are many intermediate and high level

linear correlations between on the social values, lifestyles and expectation of eating out. It can be said that there are many low, medium and high relations between the values and lifestyles of the individuals receiving service in the food and beverage enterprises which include the sampling in the broader sense.

As these results cover the relevant universe, it is considered that it would be useful to make comparisons if the study population is expanded. In addition, different personality traits can be found with different psychographic scale studies. These types of studies can be extended with participants with different personality traits and the differences between them can be measured. In addition, similar studies can be performed on different samples and may produce different results. It is considered that it will be useful both for understanding tourist behaviours and for market segmentation.

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